

A STUDY OF THE PERIODATES OF ZIRCONIUM

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3ZrO_2 , I_2O_7 , $14\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 4ZrO_2 , I_2O_7 , $18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were formed by the action of disodium paraperiodate and potassium metaperiodate on zirconium nitrate respectively. 6ZrO_2 , I_2O_7 , $20\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was formed by the action of paraperiodic acid on freshly prepared zirconium hydroxide. On dehydrating this salt, the lower hydrates were formed whose presence was confirmed by a study of their vapour pressures.

No periodates of zirconium were reported in the literature until recently when Roy Chowdhary (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 335) prepared zirconium periodate of the formula 3ZrO_2 , I_2O_7 , $17\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by the action of disodium paraperiodate on zirconium hydroxide in nitric acid solution. He has not found the available oxygen in the compound.

In the present work the periodates of zirconium have been prepared by the action of disodium paraperiodate and potassium metaperiodate on zirconium nitrate, which yielded zirconium diorthoperiodate, 3ZrO_2 , I_2O_7 , $14\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 4ZrO_2 , I_2O_7 , $18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. Another periodate of zirconium corresponding to the formula 6ZrO_2 , I_2O_7 , $20\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been obtained by the interaction of paraperiodic acid and freshly prepared zirconium hydroxide.

Disodium paraperiodate and paraperiodic acid used were prepared by Wells' method (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1901, 28, 278) as modified by Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1086). Potassium metaperiodate was prepared by the action of chlorine on a boiling solution of potassium hydroxide in presence of iodine (*cf.* Bahl and Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 167).

The analysis of the periodates of zirconium was carried out as follows. The zirconium was stimulated by changing a weighed amount of the periodate to the corresponding sulphate by heating it with strong sulphuric acid and then igniting it to a constant weight of zirconium dioxide, ZrO_2 . The available oxygen in the sample was determined by the method adopted by Partington and Bahl (*loc. cit.*). The iodine was estimated by Kimmin's method as modified by Partington and Bahl (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Salts

(a) A suspension of disodium paraperiodate in water was added gradually to an aqueous solution of excess of zirconium nitrate at room temperature with a continuous stirring. A thick white precipitate was formed immediately. (b) A bulky white precipitate was obtained by the addition of a hot solution of potassium metaperiodate to a strong solution of zirconium nitrate. (c) An excess of a dilute solution of paraperiodic acid was added, gradually with constant stirring to a thin suspension of zirconium hydroxide, freshly prepared by the action of ammonium hydroxide on a solution of zirconium nitrate and then washing it free of the soluble salts.

The precipitate obtained in each case was filtered, washed and dried at 45° in an electric air oven. The dry salts were in the form of white powders, which looked crystalline under the microscope. These were analysed for zirconium, iodine and available oxygen (Table I).

TABLE I

Sample.	Salt (a).			Salt (b).			Salt (c).		
	Zr.	I ₂ .	Available O ₂ .	Zr.	I ₂ .	Available O ₂ .	Zr.	I ₂ .	Available O ₂ .
1	28.34%	25.46%	21.05%	30.79%	21.20%	9.35%	37.29%	17.91%	7.58%
2	28.33	25.44	20.62	31.16	21.67	9.29	37.69	17.31	7.50
3	28.38	25.21	20.95	31.01	21.53	9.48	37.36	17.72	7.68

The values for salt (a) agree with the formula $3\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The calculated values for zirconium and iodine are 27.70 and 25.71% respectively. The available oxygen according to the decomposition :

The values for salt (b) correspond with the formula $4\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$; the calculated values being Zr, 30.67%; I₂, 21.47% and the available oxygen according to the equation

The calculated values for the formula $6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$ being Zr, 37.60%, I, 17.33%, and available oxygen according to the equation [cf. salt (c)]

Effect of Heat on Zirconium Periodate.

Zirconium periodate, $6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken in an uncovered weighing bottle and heated in an electric hot air oven with no loss of weight upto 60°. Above this temperature the dehydration was appreciable in the beginning but was very slow towards the end even at 100°. The different hydrates formed at the various temperatures are given below :

TABLE II

Temp.	Periodate hydrate.	Temp.	Periodate hydrate.
45°	$6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$	81°	$6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
60°	$6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$	98°	$6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$
70°	$6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$	120°	$6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7$

A study of their vapour pressures confirms the existence of all the above hydrates.

The salt was placed in a small tube connected to a vacuum pump and a manometer, which rendered a high vacuum at the room temperature. The stop-cock connecting the pump was then closed, so that only the manometer and the tube were left connected. The tube was heated in a water-bath at a constant temperature of 98°. The vapour pressures of the different hydrates as well as of the mixtures of different hydrates are given in Table III.

TABLE III

	Hydrated salt.	Vapour pressure.	Mixture of	Vapour pressure.
A.	$6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$	5.0 mm.	E+D	2.5 mm.
B.	$6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4.5	E+D+C	3.5
C.	$5\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3.5	E+D+C+B	4.5
D.	$6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.5	E+D+C+B+A	5.0
E.	$6\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.5		

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